

BSSS EARLY CAREER RESEARCHERS CONFERENCE

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KING'S HOUSE CONFERENCE CENTRE,
MANCHESTER

PANEL DISCUSSION: ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE IN AGRI-FOOD SYSTEMS

EXECUTIVE REPORT

UK Research
and Innovation

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PANEL DISCUSSION

A one-hour panel discussion on AMR in agri-food systems was held at the British Society of Soil Science (BSSS) Early Career Researchers (ECR) Conference on 2 December 2025, Manchester.

Moderated by Prof Ruben Sakrabani (Cranfield University), the session brought together experts spanning livestock, poultry, crop science, regenerative farming and veterinary perspectives. The discussion was conducted without slides or supporting materials, and the views expressed throughout represent the personal opinions of the panellists rather than those of their respective institutions.

Topics explored included sector-specific challenges, antibiotic stewardship, environmental transmission and research priorities.

PANELLISTS

Name and Organisation	Role and Expertise
Prof Ruben Sakrabani <i>Moderator</i> Cranfield University	Over 20 years of experience in soil nutrient dynamics and organic amendments. His work on organo-mineral fertilisers intersects directly with AMR challenges arising from manure feedstocks.
Dr Lisa Morgans Royal Agricultural University	Veterinarian turned applied researcher. PhD focused on farmer-led approaches to reducing antimicrobial use; now leads research on sustainable farming, slurry management and social science in animal agriculture.
Dr Mandy Nevel AHDB (Agriculture and Horticulture Development Board)	30+ years of veterinary experience in farm animal disease. Former senior lecturer at the Royal Veterinary College; expert in responsible antibiotic use and control of farm animal diseases.
Elwyn Griffiths British Egg Processors Association (BEPA) / Oaklands Farm Eggs Ltd.	Chairman of BEPA and CFO of a multi-generational family egg production business. Brings a practical, commercial perspective on antibiotic-free poultry farming and sustainable production.
Philip Taylor CABI	Plant scientist and former commercial farmer. He was involved in the Plantwise Plus programme, supporting agricultural extension services in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs); specialises in crop-level antibiotic use and biosecurity.
Tim Williams Earth Farmers	Farmer turned regenerative agriculture advisor. Focuses on soil health and biological farming systems; contributed via pre-recorded video segments.

KEY THEMES & DISCUSSION FINDINGS

AMR AS A 'SUPER WICKED' PROBLEM

Panellists framed AMR as a 'super wicked' problem: those who contribute to it are simultaneously those best placed to solve it. Simple interventions such as banning antibiotics would not eliminate resistance genes already in the environment, and could damage food security, soil fertility and rural livelihoods.

SECTOR-SPECIFIC STEWARDSHIP PROGRESS

- **Poultry:** Poultry has been a sector with early recording and stewardship efforts, and laying-hen antimicrobial use is generally low, partly because vaccination and preventive management reduce the need for treatment; however, transitions to non-cage or more extensive systems can increase disease pressure and, in some settings, antimicrobial use, with implications for AMR
- **Pigs:** The pig sector has achieved a substantial reduction in antibiotic use over the past decade, supported by quarterly recording and stewardship measures; however, AMR remains a One Health concern because antimicrobial use across environment-animal-human interfaces can select for resistant bacteria that may spread through food, environmental, and other transmission routes
- **Crops:** Antibiotic use on crops is restricted or not permitted in the UK/EU for routine agricultural purposes, whereas use on certain crops, including rice and tomatoes, has been reported in parts of Southeast Asia and other LMICs; however, the evidence base on resistance consequences in crop systems remains limited
- **Regenerative farming:** Regenerative farming may help build biologically diverse soil systems that improve resilience and potentially reduce pathogenic pressure, but more research is needed to determine whether this translates into lower reliance on antimicrobials intervention.

ENVIRONMENTAL TRANSMISSION

Soils can act as reservoirs and bioreactors for AMR genes, receiving inputs from veterinary antimicrobials, manure and slurry, sewage sludge, and other waste streams, which can enrich and disseminate ARGs in the soil microbiome

Measures such as slurry injection can alter the fate of veterinary medicines in soil, and oxytetracycline can persist long enough to affect earthworms; and thereby affect birds that feed on them. This is a reminder of unintended consequences.

Panellists called for long-term, government-funded surveillance of AMR genes in organic amendments.

EVIDENCE, POLICY & GLOBAL DIMENSIONS

Reducing antibiotic use does not always lead to an immediate fall in resistance, because resistance genes can persist in bacterial populations and spread horizontally.

In many LMIC settings, farmers may have limited awareness of AMR and may view antibiotics as routine inputs, so behaviour change is more likely to work when it is farmer-led, practical, and training-based rather than purely regulatory.

AMR is also global in scope, so domestic action alone is not sufficient given cross-border movement through trade, travel, animals, and the environment.

AUDIENCE Q&A HIGHLIGHTS

FUTURE RESEARCH PRIORITIES

Robust environmental surveillance of AMR in soil, water and air is a major knowledge and policy gap. Legislation and other incentives may be needed to drive behaviour change, because individual action alone is often insufficient.

FOOD LABELLING & CONSUMER CHOICE

Consumers may be disconnected from food production, so greater supply chain transparency is needed. Importing food produced to lower welfare or stewardship standards than those required in the UK may undermine domestic stewardship efforts.

MITIGATING AMR THROUGH SOIL AMENDMENTS

Mitigating AMR through soil amendments should focus on prevention at source, alongside improved soil and animal health. Long-term, government-funded monitoring of organic amendment quality was recommended to better understand how manure, slurry and biosolids influence AMR persistence and spread.

KEY MESSAGES

- AMR is a 'super wicked' problem requiring coordinated One Health action across animal health, human health and environmental science.
- Significant stewardship progress has been made in UK livestock sectors
- Environmental transmission via organic amendments is a major pathway that requires monitoring. Unintended consequences of management changes must be anticipated.
- Reducing antibiotic use does not automatically reduce resistance; long-term environmental surveillance is needed.
- Effective policy must be farmer-led, evidence-based and internationally coordinated.
- Early Career Researchers and Professionals in soil science and related disciplines have a vital role in environmental AMR surveillance and biologically-based farm management research.